

Invitro Antioxidant and Antidiabetic Activity of Green Synthesized Silver Nanoparticles of *Colocasia esculenta*

Shabnam Kumari Thakur¹, N V L Suvarchala Reddy V²,
M. Ganga Raju³, Oruganti Tulasi⁴, Renushri Kurva⁵, B. Rachana⁶

Gokaraju Rangaraju College of Pharmacy, Department of Pharmacology, Osmania University, Hyderabad, Telangana-500090, India

Corresponding author: *Shabnam Kumari Thakur
Assistant Professor,
Department of Pharmacology,
Gokaraju Rangaraju College of Pharmacy,
Hyderabad,
Telangana-500090, India.

Abstract

The current work uses a methanolic extract of Colocasia esculenta (MECE) leaves to create silver nanoparticles in an environmentally friendly manner. Alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, and polyphenols were found in this therapeutic plant. They converted the silver nitrate into silver nanoparticles (Ag NPs), which were then identified by Zeta potential, particle size analyser, and FT-IR. Several functional groups were found surrounding Ag NPs, according to the FT-IR data. The produced silver nanoparticles were found to be spherical in form and nano in size, according to the particle size analysis. It was discovered that the zeta potential of NPCE was -46.5 mV; this negative value validates the repulsion between the particles and, consequently, increases the formulation's stability. While evaluating the antidiabetic and antioxidant properties of the standard drugs, MECE and NPCE, it was discovered that, in comparison with MECE, NPCE greatly inhibited the enzymes that break down carbs (α Amylase) and scavenged free radicals. The results indicate that green synthesized silver nanoparticles have potential as a phytomedicine for the treatment of diabetes.

Keyword: Antidiabetic, Antioxidant, Green synthesis, Silver Nanoparticles, Phytochemical Studies

1. Introduction

Diabetes mellitus is a metabolic disorder characterized by high blood sugar levels (hyperglycaemia) caused by defects in insulin secretion or action. Its name originates from ancient Greek and Latin terms, meaning "passing through" and "honey," referring to the sweetness observed in the urine of affected individuals. If untreated, it can lead to severe complications, including ketoacidosis, coma, and even death. The condition, prevalent worldwide, causes long-term health issues such as blindness, kidney damage, neuropathy, and cardiovascular diseases. Hyperglycaemia triggers metabolic abnormalities due to insulin imbalance. Type 1 diabetes arises from autoimmune beta-cell destruction, while Type 2 results from insulin resistance and dysfunctional insulin secretion. The latter often involves hepatic insulin resistance, leading to excessive glucose production despite hyperinsulinemia. [1-2].

The well-known medicinal plant *Colocasia esculenta*, which is a member of the Araceae family and is native to Southeast Asia, is extensively grown in India. The plants antidiabetic, antioxidant effects are well documented. The leaves of *Colocasia esculenta* are used in traditional medicine as a stimulant, rubefacient, and styptic, and is used to treat internal ear aches, adenitis, haemorrhages, and buboes. Many chemicals, including terpenoids, glycosides, phenols, and flavonoids, have been extracted from the plant. (%). It also contains anthocyanins such as cyanidin 3rhamnoside, cyanidin 3-glucoside, and pelargonidin 3-glucoside. [3-4]

Furthermore, the Antioxidant activity is studied through In vitro methods using DPPH and FRAP assay, and the antidiabetic activity is studied through α -amylase inhibition assay.

The antioxidant and antidiabetic activities of *Colocasia esculenta* were synthesised and investigated in this study using a methanolic leaf extract.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Collection of plants

Botanist DR. Siddharthan from University of Hyderabad confirmed the authenticity of *Colocasia esculenta* leaves collected in November from the Hyderabad area of Telangana. The leaves were dried for about 20 days at room temperature in the shade and then finely ground using a mixer grinder. The decision was then made to retain or utilize the powdered leaves for the extraction process.

2.2. Preparation of plant extract

Twenty grams of dry *Colocasia esculenta* leaf powder was dissolved in 200 ml of methanol in a beaker and covered with aluminum foil and leave it for 8-10 days, in between shake it from time to time so the compounds which are soluble in methanol get dissolved, after that filter the product. Now evaporate the filtrate product at room temperature for 2 days. After complete evaporation of filtrate scrap out the extract which is obtained. [5-6]

2.3. Green synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles

8 gm of leaf powder was put into 200ml methanol and heated at 60°C for 15 min then cooled and supernatant was filtered using Whatman filter paper No. 1. A light green extract as clear solution was obtained and stored at 4-10°C. 2 mM solution of silver nitrate was prepared by dissolving 0.0225 gm of AgNO₃ in 75 ml of distilled water. Then 50 ml of silver nitrate solution was mixed

with 100ml of leaves extract. A colour change from light green to colloidal yellowish green black colour indicated the formation of silver nanoparticles. After 30min, 100 ml of reaction mixture was centrifuged for 5 min at 5000rpm. The solid particles as sediment were collected, washed with distilled water followed by methanol and further dried at room temperature. The dried material was analysed using FTIR, particle size analysis, zeta potential. Formation and stability of biosynthesized Ag NPs were studied using the UV-vis spectroscopic analysis. [7]

2.4. Invitro antioxidant activity

2.4.1. DPPH (2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) Method:

It is used to measure the antioxidant activity of molecules which have ability to transfer electrons. The capacity of sample extracts to reduce DPPH has been assessed by this method. The DPPH solution was prepared by dissolving 0.8mg of DPPH in 20 ml of Methanol. Plant extract and NPCE of different concentrations (20, 40, 60, 80, 100 µg/ml) was utilized followed by makeup the volume up to 3 ml with methanol.

Ascorbic acid was used as standard. Add 3ml of methanol to each test tube containing different concentration of plant extraction and silver nanoparticles. Add 1ml methanolic DPPH to each test tube. Incubate at room temperature for 30 min and measure the absorbance at 517nm and calculate IC50 value. [8]

The percent radical scavenging activity (% RSA) of the DPPH free radical was measured using the following equation:

$$\% \text{ RSA} = \{(A \text{ control} - A \text{ sample}) / (A \text{ control})\} \times 100$$

2.4.2. Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP) Assay:

The Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP) assay measures the antioxidant capacity of a sample by its ability to reduce ferric-tripyridyl triazine (Fe^{3+} - TPTZ) to ferrous-tripyridyl triazine (Fe^{2+} - TPTZ).

Plant extract, silver nanoparticles, Ascorbic acid (standard) were made into five different concentrations (20, 40, 60, 80, 100 µg/ml).

1ml of plant extract is added to 2.5ml of sodium phosphate buffer of 0.2M, then add 2.5ml of 1% potassium ferricyanide and incubate at 50°C for 20min. After incubation add 2.5ml of 10% Trichloroacetic acid and centrifuge the mixture at 4000rpm for 10min.

Collect 2.5ml of supernatant, to this add 2.5ml of water and 0.5ml of 0.1% FeCl_3 and incubate it for 8 min at 25°C and measure the absorbance at 700nm on the UV visible spectrophotometer. [9]

2.5. Invitro antidiabetic activity

2.5.1. α -Amylase inhibition assay

Procedure

Plant extract, Nano particle and Acarbose standard of different concentrations (20, 40, 60, 80, 100) are taken in test tubes.

1. Take 1ml of plant extract (in 5 test tubes of different conc.), then add 10 μ l α -amylase and 890 μ l phosphate buffer.
2. Now incubate each test tube for 10min at 37⁰C.
3. After incubation add 100 μ l of starch solution and incubate for 1 hour.
4. After incubation add 0.1ml of 1% iodine solution and 5ml of distilled water to all the test tubes.
5. Finally check the absorbance at 565nm.
6. Repeat all the above steps for Nano particles and acarbose standard of different concentrations. [10-11]

3. Result and Discussion

The invitro antioxidant and antidiabetic activity of green synthesized silver nanoparticles of *Colocasia esculenta* was explored for its potential antidiabetic effects. All the results obtained in the study are outlined below.

Preliminary Phytochemical analysis

The preliminary phytochemical investigation of the methanolic extract of *Colocasia esculenta* leaves (MECE) revealed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, tannins, and polyphenols.

Table 1. Preliminary Phytochemical analysis

Phytochemical Constituents	Results
Alkaloids	++
Flavonoids	++
Saponins	++
Tannins	++
Polyphenols	++

Note: + indicates present; - indicates absent

UV-Spectral Analysis

Formation of silver nanoparticle was further checked by UV–Visible spectroscopy. A broad absorption peak was observed at 415 nm as shown in the figure. this band corresponds to the absorption by colloidal silver nanoparticles in the region (400–450 nm) due to the excitation of surface plasmon vibration.

Figure 1: UV–Visible spectra of synthesized Ag NPs

In vitro antioxidant assay

The Ascorbic acid, MECE and NPCE were subjected to *in vitro* antioxidant assays. The *in vitro* antioxidant activity was assessed using the DPPH (2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) Method and FRAP Assay (Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power).

DPPH scavenging assay

Figure 2: DPPH scavenging assay of Ascorbic acid, MECE and NPCE

DPPH assay, IC₅₀ values of standard drug, MECE and NPCE was found to be 42.8, 56.3 and 46.7 µg/ml respectively. From the above result it is clear that NPCE showed good antioxidant activity. The results were expressed in the table 2 and the profile was expressed in the figure 2

FRAP assay of Ascorbic acid, MECE and NPCE:**Figure 3** FRAP assay of Ascorbic acid, MECE and NPCE

FRAP assay, IC₅₀ values of standard drug, MECE and NPCE was found to be 42, 48.5 and 46.4 µg/ml respectively. From the above result it is clear that NPCE showed good antioxidant activity. The results were expressed in the table 3 and the profile was expressed in the figure 3.

Invitro antidiabetic activity

The Acarbose, MECE and NPCE were subjected to invitro antidiabetic activity. The invitro antidiabetic activity was performed and assessed using α – amylase.

 α – amylase inhibitory assay:**Figure 4:** α – amylase inhibitory assay of Acarbose, MECE and NPCE

α -amylase inhibition assay, IC₅₀ values of standard drug, MECE and NPCE was found to be 47.4, 57.4 and 51.6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively. From the above result it is clear that NPCE showed good α -amylase inhibition activity when compared to MECE. The results were expressed in the table 4 and the profile was expressed in the figure 4.

FT-IR SPECTROSCOPIC ANALYSIS

FT-IR measurements were performed to identify the potential biomolecules in the leaves of *Colocasia esculenta* responsible for the formation of silver nanoparticles. The FT-IR spectrum of the methanolic leaf extract of *Colocasia Esculenta* before reaction showed several absorption peaks at 3437, 2974, 2870, 2374, 1637, 1398, 1149, 1020, 1057, and 422 cm^{-1} . The FT-IR spectrum of the silver nanoparticles exhibited absorption peaks at 3419, 2924, 2843, 1641, 1379, 1055, 1014, 1055, 2359 and 432 cm^{-1} . These peaks correspond to O-H stretching (alcohols, amides), C-H stretching (alkanes, ethers), O-H stretching (carboxylic acids), C-H bending (aromatic compounds), C=C=C (allene), C=C (conjugated alkene), O-H bending (phenols), C-O stretching (esters), C-N stretching (amines), and C-Cl stretching (halo compounds). The analysis of the plant extract using FT-IR measurements confirmed the presence of active biomolecules that acted as capping and reducing agents. The functional groups present in the sample may be responsible for the bio-reduction of Ag^+ to Ag nanoparticles.

Fig 5.1: FTIR OF NPCE

Fig 5.2 FTIR OF MECE

Particle size and zetapotential:

NPCE:

The particle size and zeta potential for the nanoparticles of *Colocasia Esculenta* were found to be 126 nm and -46.5 mV, respectively. The zeta potential indicates the charge on the particle surface, which reflects the physical stability of the dispersed system. A high zeta potential confers stability to the preparation, helping to resist aggregation.

Fig 6: Particle size of NPCE

Fig 7: Zeta Potential of NPCE

4. Conclusion

The plant was collected, and its constituents were extracted using a methanol-based maceration method. Conventional methods were then applied to the resulting extract for further analysis. An initial phytochemical examination of the *Colocasia esculenta* methanolic extract was conducted, revealing the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, tannins and polyphenols. The in vitro antioxidant activity was performed using DPPH assay and FRAP assay. The result showed prominent antioxidant property for NPCE when compared to MECE.

The prominent antidiabetic action was performed using alpha amylase inhibitory assay. The result showed prominent antidiabetic property for NPCE when compared to MECE.

Silver Nanoparticles of *Colocasia esculenta* was formulated and evaluated for Particle size, Zeta potential and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy. It may be concluded that Nanoparticle of *Colocasia esculenta* has significant antioxidant and antidiabetic activity. The obtained results are

significant, but further studies are required to confirm its precise mechanism of action through in-vivo models for the recommendation of this product as a therapeutic medicine for diabetes.

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5. Reference

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